

**MURIVENNA: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW WITH RESPECT TO THE
MANAGEMENT OF ABHIGATAJA VRANA****Dr. Isuwarya Bharany S.^{1*}, Dr. Saran Babu², Dr. Vikram S.³, Dr. Sorubini Loganathan⁴**

¹PG Scholar, Department of PG Studies in Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru, Karnataka.

²Associate Professor, Department of PG Studies in Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru, Karnataka.

³Professor, HOD, Department of PG Studies in Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru, Karnataka.

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of PG Studies in Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru, Karnataka.

***Corresponding Author: Dr. Isuwarya Bharany S.**

PG Scholar, Department of PG Studies in Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru, Karnataka. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18874726>

How to cite this Article: Dr. Isuwarya Bharany S.^{1*}, Dr. Saran Babu², Dr. Vikram S.³, Dr. Sorubini Loganathan⁴ (2026). Murivenna: A Comprehensive Review With Respect To The Management Of Abhigataja Vrana. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(3), 505–514.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 05/02/2026

Article Revised on 25/02/2026

Article Published on 05/03/2026

ABSTRACT

Murivenna is a classical Kerala based *Ayurvedic* medicated *Taila* traditionally indicated in the management of *Abhigatajanya* conditions such as wounds, fractures, burns, and soft tissue injuries. *Acharya Sushruta* has elaborately described *Vrana* and its management under *Shashti Upakrama* where *Taila* is used for the management of *Vrana*. Though not described in *Brhatrayi*, *Murivenna* is mentioned in *Agastya Marma Shastra* and *Siddha Ayurveda* practices. And later it is incorporated into the *Ayurvedic* Formulary of India as an *Anubhuta Yoga*. The formulation is specifically intended for *Abhigatajanya* conditions, where early therapeutic intervention plays a crucial role in preventing complications such as chronic pain, stiffness, fibrosis, and delayed wound healing. The present review aims to analyse *Murivenna* with respect to its references, formulation variations in ingredients and indications. Also, review on method of preparation, *Rasa Panchaka*, and therapeutic rationale in *Vrana* and *Bhagna* management. Classical *Ayurvedic* texts including *Yoga Manjari*, *Chikitsa Manjari*, *Marma Shastra Peedika*, and AFI were reviewed to compile the formulation. According to AFI the formulation consists of Drugs like *Karanja*, *Nagavalli*, *Sigru*, *Paribhadra*, *Palandu*, *Vasuka*, *Tandulodaka*, and *Shatavari*. *Rasa Panchaka* analysis of above drugs reveals predominance of *Tikta*, *Katu*, and *Madhura Rasa* with *Ushna Veerya*, *Katu Vipaka*, and *Snigdha-Laghu-Teekshna-Sara Guna*, rendering the formulation predominantly *Vata-Kapha Shamaka*. These properties contribute to *Shothahara*, *Vedanasthapana*, *Vrana Shodhana*, and *Vrana Ropana* actions.

KEYWORDS: *Abhigata Chikitsa*, *Murivenna*, *Vrana*.**INTRODUCTION**

Acharya Sushruta had broadly explained *Vrana* and its *Chikitsa*. Detailed explanation of *Vrana Chikitsa* and its importance is described in *Shashti Upakrama*. Application of *Taila* is one among them.^[1]

In *Ayurveda*, *Taila Kalpana* plays a crucial role in management of *Vrana*, *Shotha* and *Marmabhighata* where a single formulation is expected to provide *Twachya*, *Vedanasthapana*, *Shothagna* and *Vranaropaka* actions simultaneously. In this Therapeutic context,

Murivenna is *Taila* based formulation used by *Siddha* practitioners of Tamil Nadu & Kerala for wound healing and soft tissue injury management since olden days.

Murivenna is not mentioned in *Brhatrayi*, rather it has its roots in Kerala practice and *Agastya Marma* traditions, later accepted into the *Ayurvedic Formulary of India*^[2] as a validated regional *Anubhuta Yoga*.

The formulation consists of Drugs like *Karanja*, *Nagavalli*, *Sigru*, *Paribhadra*, *Palandu*, *Vasuka*, *Tandula*,

and Shatavari. Overall Rasa Panchaka analysis reveals predominance of Tikta, Katu, and Madhura Rasa with Ushna Veerya, Katu Vipaka, and Snigdha, Laghu, Teekshna & Sara Guna rendering the formulation predominantly Vata-Kapha Shamaka. These properties contribute to Shothahara, Vedanasthapana, Vrana Shodhana, and Vrana Ropana actions, as described in classical Ayurvedic texts.

The method of preparation with controlled Paka imparts qualities like Sukshma, Teekshna and Sheegra Vyapthi enabling the drug to penetrate quickly and act effectively in the acute phase of injury, when early intervention can prevent stiffness, fibrosis and chronic pain.

In the present work, an attempt is made to analyse the specific Guṇa Karma of its ingredients to understand

how Murivenna mediates these effects at the site of injury.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

I. FORMULATION REVIEW

First reference of Murivenna is available in Agastya Marma Kannadi which is a Siddha textbook. Various references are also available in text books like Chikitsa Manjari, Yoga Manjari, Marma Shastra Samaharam by Kanjiramkulam K. Kochi Krishna Nadar & Marma Shastra Peedika by M. Kunju Krishna Nadar MLA. It is also known as Kshatantaka tailam.

More than 20 different varieties of Murivenna have been described. Some of them are listed below.

Table No 1: Murivenna Formulations with Ingredient Variations and References.

S.No	Formulation	Ingredients and Proportions	Reference and Indications
1.	<i>Murivenna</i> ^[2]	<p>Kalka Dravya: Shatavari – 144g</p> <p>Sneha Dravya: Narikela taila- 768ml</p> <p>Drava Dravya: Tandulodaka – 768ml Tambula Patra Swarasa– 384g Vasuka Swarasa– 384g Palandu swarasa – 384g Sigrupatra swarasa– 384g Paribhadra patra rasa– 384g Kanya rasa– 384g Karanja patra swarasa-384 g</p>	<p>AFI Part III</p> <p>Indication: Vrana, Sandhi shopha, Abhigatajanya Shopha, Asthi Bhagna Sandhi chutha</p>
2.	<i>Nalpamaradi Murivenna</i> ^[3]	<p>Kalka Dravya: Chitraka, Kupilu moola, Karanja Twak, Shigru twak, Ketaki moola, Shunti, Shallaki, Saindhava -10gm each</p> <p>Sneha Dravya: Narikela taila – 2 liters</p> <p>Drava Dravya: Nalpamara twak-250gm Narikela Jala – 8 liters Narikela Tantu rasa(Husk) – 8 liters</p>	<p>Marma Shastra Peedika</p> <p>Indication: Vrana</p>
3.	<i>Kayaranjakam Murivenna</i> ^[3]	<p>Kalka Dravya: 1 Karsha each Krishna jeeraka, Bakuchi, Yashtimadhu, Dineshavalli, Hareetaki</p> <p>Sneha Dravya: Narikela taila – 1.5 L</p> <p>Kwatha Dravya: Nalpamaram Twak – 4 Pala Paranthi Pushpa – 4 Pala Sariva - 1 Pala</p> <p>Drava Dravya: Vishnukranti, Dhurva, Bhringarajaa, Kakamachi, Musali, Dasapushpam, Moringa, Kupeelu, Paribadra, Sushavi, Haridra – 192 gm each</p> <p>Paka: Taila prepared by Sneha Paka Vidhi; Beeswax added to obtain Patra Paka Taila.</p>	<p>Marma Shastra Peedika</p> <p>Indication: - Dhara in Bhagna, Vrana - Abhyanga</p>
4.	<i>Kumaryadi</i>	<p>Kalka Dravya:</p>	<p>Marma Shastra Peedika</p>

	Murivenna^[3]	<i>Kupilu</i> – 60gm Sneha Dravya – <i>Narikela taila</i> – 350 ml Drava Dravya: <i>Kumari, Tambula, Shigru Patra, Paribadra leaves</i> – Swarasa 150ml each <i>Vasuka Swarasa</i> <i>Karanja Bark rasa</i> <i>Palandu Swarasa</i>	Indication: <i>Vrana</i>
5	Murivenna^[4]	Sneha Dravya <i>Narikela taila</i> – 1 Litre Drava Dravya <i>Vranaropini, Lajjalu, Durva,</i> (each 2 <i>Mushti Pramana</i>) <i>Krishna Jeeraka</i> – 2 <i>Pala</i> <i>Shallaki</i> – ½ <i>kalanja</i> (2gm) Dried Pulp of <i>Kumari</i> - ½ <i>kalanja</i> (2gm) <i>Dineshavalli</i> – 4 <i>kalanja</i> (16gm)	<i>Marma Shastra Peedika</i> Indication: <i>Vrana</i>
6.	Murivenna^[4]	Kalka Dravya: <i>Nirgundi, Bilwa, Bala, Haridra, Shankhapushpi, Kutaja,</i> <i>Paribhadra</i> – 5 <i>pala</i> each <i>Jeeraka</i> – 1 <i>Pala</i> <i>Mahameda, Lavanga</i> – 1 <i>Karsha</i> each Sneha Dravya: <i>Tila taila</i> – 1 litre <i>Ghrita</i> – added at final stage (to get wax like consistency)	<i>Marma shastraPpeedika</i> Indication: <i>Vrana</i>
7.	Murivenna^[4]	Kalka Dravya: <i>Karanja, Nimba, Haridra, Tambula Patra, Pura</i> – 1/4 th part Sneha Dravya: <i>Narikela taila</i> – 1 part Drava Dravya: <i>Ksheera</i> - 1 part <i>Swarasa of Kumari, Shigru, Paribadra</i> – ½ parts each	<i>Marma shastra Peedika</i> Indication: <i>Vrana, Bhagna, Snayu kshata, Asthi sambanda roga.</i>
8.	Murivenna^[4]	Kalka Dravya: <i>Sudha Churna</i> – 1/4 th part Sneha Dravya: <i>Tila Taila</i> – 1 part Drava Dravya: <i>Kumari Swarasa</i> – ½ part <i>Ksheera</i> – ½ part Kashaya Dravya: <i>Vata, Bala, Sareeva, Kutaja moola</i> – 240ml	<i>Marma Shastra Peedika</i> Indication: <i>Vrana</i>

Few other indications of *Murivenna* are mentioned in *Yoga Manjari*^[5] even though the ingredients are same as that of AFI.

Table no 2: Indications Mentioned in *Yoga Manjari*.^[5]

Indication	Mode of Administration
<i>Abhighatajanya Vrana</i> / Bruise	External application, <i>Lepana, Bandhana</i>
Sports injury	External application over affected area
<i>Katigraha</i> with <i>Teevra Vedana</i>	<i>Basti, Pichu</i>
<i>Asthi Bhagna</i> / <i>Sandhi Bhagna</i> with <i>Sadya Vrana</i>	<i>Bandhana</i>
<i>Shalya Tantra Pradhana Rogas</i>	<i>Seka, Abhyanga</i>
<i>Dagdha</i> (Burns)	Immediate <i>Dhara</i> , External application
<i>Abhighataja Shopha</i>	With <i>Kottamchukkadi Taila</i>
Bruise / <i>Vedana</i>	With <i>Dhanwantaram Taila</i>
<i>Lakshanika Karma</i> – <i>Nirama Shopha</i>	External application for <i>Shophahara</i>
<i>Sandhigata Vata Shopha</i> + <i>Arshas</i>	External application (as per Dr. K. Murali)
<i>Vata Roga (Nirama Avastha)</i>	<i>Abhyanga, Pichu</i>
<i>Danta Shoola</i>	<i>Gandusha</i> (as per <i>Ashtavaidyan P.T.N. Vasudevan</i>)

Internal use (as per Vaidya Kutti Krishnan)	<i>Gandusha</i>
Contraindication	Not used for <i>Shiro Abhyanga</i>

Method of Preparation

Murivenna is prepared using various *Drava Dravya* in the medium of *Narikela Taila*. The *Kalka* is added and the mixture is heated and kept aside for a day. The same

process is repeated on the subsequent days, and heating of the *Taila* is continued for three days. When *Sneha Siddhi Lakshanas* are attained, the *Taila* is filtered, allowed to cool, and stored in airtight containers.

1) NAGAVALLI^[6,7]

Botanical Name - *Piper betel* Linn.

Family – Piperaceae

Rasa	Katu, Tikta, Kasaya
Guna	Laghu, Sara, Tikshna
Virya	Ushna
Vipaka	Katu
Doshagnatha	Vata Kapha Hara
Karma	Balya, Ruchya, Sramahara, Mukhadourgandhyahara, Svarya, Vrsya
Vernacular names	English - Betel Leaf, Sanskrit – Tambuli, Hindi – Pan, Kannada - Veelyadele Ele, Tamil – Vettilai, Malayalam – Vettilla, Telugu - Tamalapaku,
Synonyms	Tambulavalli, Tambuli, Nagini, Nagavallari, Tambula, Nagavalli
Prayojya Anga	Patra
Chemical constituents	Eugenol, Hydroxychavicol, Essential Oil, Amino Acids, Vitamins and Enzymes,
Rogagnatha	Kandu, Hrllasa, Agnimandhya, Jwara, Hrdroga, Swarabheda.
Morphology	Leaf - Varies greatly in size, 7.5 - 20.0 cm, ovate cordate, entire, glabrous, apex acuminate to acute, lamina membranous, upper surface deep green and lower surface lighter in colour, primary or sub primary nerves usually seven, sometimes 5-9. Odour - Aromatic Taste - Slightly pungent

2) KUMARI^[8,9]

Botanical Name - *Aloe barbadensis* Linn.

Family – Liliaceae

Rasa	Tikta, Madhura
Guna	Guru, snigdha, Picchila
Virya	Sheeta
Vipaka	Katu
Doshagnatha	Tridosha Shamaka
Karma	Caksusya, Vrsya, Brmhana, Rasayana, Bhedana, Kushtagna, Krimigna, Jwarahara
Dhatu	Mamsa, Shukra, Rasa, Rakta, Meda
Vernacular names	English - Indian aloe, Sanskrit – Ghrithakumari, Hindi – Ghikuvaar, Kannada – Lolisara, Tamil – kattalai, Malayalam – Katarvazha, Telugu – Kalabanda
Synonyms	Kumari, Gruhakanya, Kanya, Ghrutakumarika
Prayojya Anga	Patra
Chemical constituents	Aloe-Emodin, aloenin, β -Sitosterol, barbaloin, galactose, Vitamin A & B.
Rogagnatha	Agni dagddha visphota, Twak vikara, Kusta, Krimi, Yakrut vikara, Kamala, Vibandha.
Morphology	Parenchyma rich in chlorophyll cells show starch and bundles of needle of calcium oxalate. Central portion consists of mucilage containing parenchyma. A double row of vascular bundles located at the junction of the two preceding areas and with well marked pericycle and endodermis. Dried juice (leaves): it varies in colour from yellow brown to chocolate brown. It breaks with a waxy fracture giving a sour odour. Taste is bitter. Drug shows (examined in lactophenol microscopically) crystals of aloin embedded in masses of resin.

3) **KARANJA**^[10,11]

Botanical Name - *Pongamia pinnata* Linn

Family – Fabaceae

Rasa	Katu, Tikta, Kashaya
Guna	<i>Laghu, Teekshna</i>
Viryā	<i>Ushna</i>
Vipaka	<i>Katu</i>
Doshagnatha	<i>Kapha Vata hara</i>
Karma	<i>Kandugna, Vishagna, Vrana shodhana</i>
Dhatu	<i>Meda, Rakta</i>
Vernacular names	English – Pongamia ; Sanskrit – Ghritakaranja, Naktamala; Hindi - Karanj; Kannada - Honge Beru; Tamil – Pungai; Malayalam – Pungu, Ungu; Urdu – Karanj; Telugu – Ganuga, Kanuga
Synonyms	<i>Karanja, Naktamala, Chirabilwa</i>
PrayojyaAnga	<i>Bark</i>
Chemical constituents	Flavones and Furanoflavones like Karanjin, Pongapin, Demethoxy-kanugin, Kanugin, Pinnatin, Tetra-o-Methylfisetin, Gamatin, 5-Methoxyfurano (2", 3" 7 : 8), flavone and 5-Methoxy-3'4' Methylene dioxyfurano (2", 3", 7 : 8) flavone & two new Furano compounds Glabra-I and Glabra-II. It also contains alkaloids and Triterpenoid saponin.
Rogagnatha	<i>Kusta, Kandu, Dusta vrana, Prameha, Yoni roga, Krimi roga, Antra vidradhi, Vidradhi.</i>
Morphology	Bark available in channelled, recurved, slightly quilled, usually 0.2-1 cm thick, lenticellate pieces, more or less smooth; outer surface ash-grey to greyish-brown and internal surface yellowish-white to cream coloured; fracture, short and fibrous, odour, unpleasant; taste, bitter.

4) **SIGRU**^[12,13]

Botanical Name - *Moringa oleifera* Lam.

Family – Moringaceae

Rasa	Katu, Tikta
Guna	<i>Laghu, Ruksha, Teekshna</i>
Viryā	<i>Ushna</i>
Vipaka	<i>Katu</i>
Doshagnatha	<i>Vata kapha Shamaka</i>
Karma	<i>Krimihara, Chaksushya, Brimhana. Kusthaghna, Sulahara, Swayathuhara</i>
Dhatu	<i>Meda, Rakta, Asthi</i>
Vernacular names	English – Drumstick tree; Sanskrit – Sobhanjana; Hindi – Shajoma, Mungna; Kannada – Neegee; Tamil – Murungai ; Malayalam – Muringya, Murinna; Telugu - Munaga aku
Synonyms	<i>Shobhanjana, Sigru , Teekshna gandhaka , Akshiva, Mochaka</i>
Prayojya Anga	<i>Patra</i>
Chemical constituents	Quercetin, Kaempferol, Carbohydrate, Protein, Carotene and Ascorbic acid.
Rogagnatha	<i>Sopha, Sula, Krimiroga, Medoroga, Pleeharoga, Vidradhi, Gulma, Galaroga</i>
Morphology	Leaves tripinnate compound, available in the form of leaflets and some broken pieces of rachis, slender, thickened, and articulated at the base; leaflet 1.2-2 cm long and 0.5-1 cm wide, entire, elliptic, ovate or obovate, rounded or narrowed at base and obtuse at apex; smooth and greenish-grey to pale green; odour and taste not distinct.

5) **PARIBHADRA**^[14,15]

Botanical Name – *Erythrina indica* Lamk

Family – Fabaceae

Rasa	Tikta, Katu
Guna	<i>Sara, Laghu</i>
Viryā	<i>Ushna</i>
Vipaka	<i>Katu</i>
Doshagnatha	<i>Vata-kapha hara</i>
Karma	<i>Medohara, Krimigna</i>
Vernacular names	English – Indian Coral Tree; Sanskrit – Paribhadra, Kantakimshuka; Hindi – Pharahada; Kannada – Hongar; Tamil - Mulmurungai ; Malayalam - Murrikku ;Telugu – Badisa.
Synonyms	<i>Paribhadra, Nimbataru, Mandara, Parijataka</i>

<i>Prayojya Anga</i>	<i>Patra</i>
Chemical constituents	Hupaphorine, erysotrine and erythreoline.
Rogagnatha	Karnaroga, Vrana & Granthi Shotha, Krimiroga, Netrabhisyanda, Anidra, Aruchi, Raktavikara, Kushta, Medoroga.
Morphology	A deciduous tree armed with short sharp conical black prickles arising from woody tubercles; bark thin, yellowish; wood white, soft. Branches are woddy sticks or twigs quite weak or breakable (suggesting care in tree climbing). Leaves glabrescent, 3-foliolate; petioles 10-20 cm. long unarmed; leaflets broadly ovate or rhomboid, acuminate, entire, 10-20 cm. long and broad, membranous, glabrescent, lateral ones oblique. Racemes 10-15 cm, long, clustered at the end of leafless branchelets. Calyx spathaceous, recurved, truncate at mouth, 5-toothed at the narrow tip; calyx clothed with deciduous tomentum, mouth very oblique.

6) *PALANDU*^[16,17]

Botanical Name – *Alium cepa* Linn

Family – Liliaceae

Rasa	Katu, Madhura
<i>Guna</i>	<i>Snigdha, Teekshna, Guru</i>
<i>Virya</i>	<i>Ushna</i>
<i>Vipaka</i>	<i>Madhura</i>
<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Majja, Rakta, Shukra</i>
<i>Doshagnatha</i>	<i>Vata Kapha Hara</i>
<i>Karma</i>	<i>Kaphanisaraka, uttejaka, Vrsya, Balya</i>
Vernacular names	English – Onion; Sanskrit – Palandu; Hindi – Piyaj; Kannada - Irulli, Nirulli; Tamil – Vengayam; Malayalam – Bavang; Telugu – Nirulli
Synonyms	<i>Palandu, Yavaneshtha, Durgandha, Mukhadushika</i>
<i>Prayojya Anga</i>	Bulb of onion
Chemical constituents	Cycloallin, Oleanolic acid, arabinose, xylose, ribose, quercetin, thiopropanal -S-oxide, catechol, beta- sitosterol, ferulic acids, beta- amyryn, phenolic acids, allylpropyl disulphide, thiosulfinate, cholesterol, propenyl sulfenic acids.
<i>Rogagnatha</i>	<i>Vata vyadhi, Naadi shola, Vrana Shotha, Karna Shoola, Rakta pitta, Kasa, Swasa, Hikka, Vibhandha.</i>
Morphology	Scapigerous herb with globose, tunicated, fleshy, underground bulb 5-10cm in diameter, odour characteristic. Leaves sub- distichous, 30-60 cm long, fistular, acute, glaucous – green. Flowers greenish -white, numerous in globose umbels 3-10cm in diam. Scape 30 – 90cm long, terete, fistular with many flowered umbels at the apex; bracts spathaceous, membranous, ovate – lanceolate. Capsule globose, membranous; seeds compressed, angular, black, shining.

7) *VASUKA*^[18,19]

Botanical Name - *Borreria hispida* Linn

Family – Rubiaceae

Rasa	Katu, Tikta
<i>Guna</i>	<i>Ruksha, Tiksna</i>
<i>Virya</i>	<i>Usna</i>
<i>Vipaka</i>	<i>Katu</i>
<i>Doshagnatha</i>	<i>Kapha pitta hara</i>
<i>Karma</i>	<i>Vishahara, Vranahara</i>
Vernacular names	English – Shaggy button weed; Sanskrit – Vasukah, Buka, Madanghanti; Hindi – Madanaghanti; Kannada - Madanabadu, Megidda; Tamil – Nathaichuri; Malayalam – Tartaval; Telugu – Madana, Madana Budatha kaada
Synonyms	<i>Shivamalli, Pashupata, Ekasthila, Baka, Buka, Vasu</i>
<i>Prayojya Anga</i>	<i>Patra</i>
Chemical constituents	Bark contains 2 resins and a bitter poisonous alkaloid, which is also present in leaves. The alkaloids traced are Erisodin, Erisoin, Erisonin and Erisotrin, Oeirntin, Ursolic acid. Seeds contain about 10-30% of oils.
<i>Rogagnatha</i>	<i>Yonidosha, Trushna, Daha, Kusta, Shotha, Raktavikara</i>
Morphology	A hispid procumbent with long branches and quadrangular stems; leaves simple, opposite,

	subsessile, oblong or elliptic, scabrid, flowers pale mauve usually long tubed, 4-6 in a whorl within the stipular cup, fruits capsules, ellipsoid, rounded at both ends, 5 mm long, rounded on the back with a deep groove on the flat face. The bark and leaves are having anti-inflammatory property.
--	--

8) SHATAVARI^[20,21]

Botanical Name -*Asparagus racemosus* Wild.

Family – Liliaceae

Rasa	Madhura, Tikta
Guna	Guru, Snigdha
Virya	Sheeta
Vipaka	Madhura
Doshagnatha	Vatapitta hara
Dhatu	Rasa, Rakta, Majja, Shukra
Karma	Rasayana, Medhya, Pusti Vardhaka, Netrya, Vrishya, Sukravardhaka
Vernacular names	English – Asparagus; Sanskrit – Shatavari; Hindi – Satavar, Satamul; Kannada – Ashadi poeru, Halavu Bau; Tamil – Shimai -Shasvari; Malayalam – Satavari Kizhangu
Synonyms	<i>Shatamuli, Bahusuta, Narayani, Vari, Shatapadi, Peevari, Indivari, Rushyaprokta, Urdhvakantika, Bhiru</i>
Prayojya Anga	Tubers (Kanda)
Chemical constituents	Sugar, Glycosides, Saponin and Sitosterol. Shatavarin I- IV, Quercetin, Asparagamine
Rogagnatha	<i>Shotha, Kshaya, Parinama sula, Gulma, Atisara, Raktatisara, Mutravikara, Amlapitta, Arsas, Visarpa, Sutika roga.</i>
Morphology	Root tuberous, 10 to 30 cm in length and 0.1 to 0.5 cm thick, tapering at both ends with longitudinal wrinkles; colour cream; taste, sweetish.

9) TANDULA^[22,23]

Botanical Name –*Oryza sativa* Linn.

Family – Gramineae

Rasa	Madhura, Kashaya
Guna	Snigdha, Laghu
Virya	Sheeta
Vipaka	Madhura
Doshagnatha	Vata Pitta Hara
Karma	Balya, Brimhana, Sukrala, Swarya, Ruchya, Vrushya, Mutrala
Vernacular names	English – Rice, Paddy; Sanskrit – Shali; Hindi – Chaval, Dhana; Kannada – Bhatto, Akki; Tamil – Arisi, Nelver; Malayalam – Ari, Nelli; Urdu – Chaval, Biranj; Telugu – Dhanyamu.
Synonyms	<i>Raktashali, Mahashali, Kalama, Shakunahrut, Deerghasuka, Panduka, Sugandhaka, Pundarika, Kanchana, Mahisha, Dushaka, Kardama.</i>
Prayojya Anga	Seed (grain)
Chemical constituents	Ferulic acid, Gamma oryzanol, Albuminoids, fats, carbohydrates, fibres,
Rogagnatha	<i>Jwara, Trishna, Atisara, Pradara.</i>
Morphology	It is Harvested all over the India. It is a small, watery and yearly shrub. Stem – Hollow and Round Leaf – Many in number, rough surface, small in shape and spear shaped. Flower – In bulk, with many branches and bent. It has stamen 6 in numbers and pistil which are 2 in number and shaped just like its leaves.

10) NARIKELA^[24,25]

Botanical Name – *Cocos nucifera* Linn.

Family – Palmaceae

Rasa	Madhura
Guna	Guru, Snigdha
Virya	Sheeta
Vipaka	Madhura
Doshagnatha	Pittahara

<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Rasa, Rakta, Shukra, Mamsa, Medha, Majja</i>
<i>Karma</i>	<i>Basti shodhana, Balya, Brimhana, Raktahara, Ruchya</i>
Vernacular names	English – Coconut Tree; Sanskrit – Narikela, Trnaraja; Hindi – Nariyal, Gola; Kannada – Khobbari, Tengnamara; ; Tamil – Tenkai, Kopparai; Malayalam – Nalikeram, Ten, Thengu, Keram; Telugu – Narikelamu, Tenkay, Kobbari
Synonyms	<i>Kurcha, sheershaka, Thunga, Truna raja, Drudaphala, Langali, Sadhaphala Skandhaphala</i>
<i>Prayojya Anga</i>	Fruit
Chemical constituents	Fixed Oil
<i>Rogagnatha</i>	<i>Daha, Kshata, Kshaya, Raktapitta, Trushna, Shosha, Shoola.</i>
Morphology	Drug available whole as well as in broken pieces of endosperm, whole drug 8-14 cm in size; ovoid, three angled, outer surface brown, somewhat rough due to shallow, reticulated striations; transversely broken; whole drug shows 0.8-1.2 cm thick, white endosperm and a large central cavity; fracture, short; odour, faint; taste, sweetish and oily.

DISCUSSION

Table no 3: Assessing Rasa Panchaka of Ingredients of Murivenna Taila.

S.no	Ingredients	Rasa	Guna	Veerya	Vipaka	Dosha Karma
1	<i>Nagavalli</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta, Kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu, Sara, Teekshna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Vata Kapha hara</i>
2	<i>Kumari</i>	<i>Tikta, Madhura</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha, Picchila</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Tridosha hara</i>
3	<i>Karanja</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta, Kashya</i>	<i>Laghu, Teekshna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kapha Vata hara</i>
4	<i>Shigru</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha, Teekshna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Vata Kapha hara</i>
5	<i>Paribhadra</i>	<i>Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Sara, laghu</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Vata Kapha hara</i>
6	<i>Palandu</i>	<i>Katu, Madhura</i>	<i>Snigdha, Teekshna, Sara</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Vata Kapha hara</i>
7	<i>Vasuka</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>	<i>Ruksha, Teekshna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kapha Pitta hara</i>
8	<i>Shatavari</i>	<i>Madhura, Tikta</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Vata Pitta hara</i>
9	<i>Tandula</i>	<i>Madhura, Kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Vata Pitta hara</i>

Overall Rasa Panchaka of Murivenna

Rasa – *Tikta, Katu, Madhura*

Guna – *Snigdha, Laghu, Teekshna, Sara*

Veerya – *Ushna*

Vipaka - *Katu*

Doshahara - *Vata Kapha Hara.*

As majorly it is *Tikta Rasa Pradhana* -

- It is *Vishagna, Krimigna, Kanduhara, Kustahara, Dahahara*
- Gives Stability to *Twak* and *Mamsa* also does *Pachana, Lekhana*
- Does *Upashoshana* of *Puya, Kleda, Meda, Majja, Pitta* and *Sleshma* etc.

Katu Rasa Karma

- Removes *Kleda* and *Swayathu hara*
- Kandu* and *Krimi hara*
- Vranan Avasadayathi, Mamsam Vilikathi, Shonitha Sangatham Bhinathi* (breaks Bonds of Blood), *Margan Vivrunothi* (clarify the passages).

The predominance of *Tikta* and *Katu Rasa* supports removal of *Kleda*, control of infection, and reduction of swelling, while *Madhura Rasa* and *Snigdha Guna* assist in tissue nourishment and structural restoration. Through

Ushna Veerya, the formulation counteracts aggravated *Vata*, thereby reducing pain and stiffness, and at the same time facilitates proper circulation at the affected area. When processed in *Narikela Taila*, these properties gain enhanced penetration and sustained local action, making the formulation suitable even in delicate conditions such as burns. *Murivenna* acts through a coordinated mechanism involving *Shothahara, Vedanasthapana, Vrana Shodhana* and *Vrana Ropana* effects.

When *Murivenna* is applied externally over the wound, the *Sneha* enters through *Romakupa* and the damaged *Tvak Marga*, spreading through *Sukshma Srotas* due to its *Sukshma* and *Vyavayi Guna*. It reaches *Rasa Dhatu* and *Rakta Dhatu*, supporting *Dhatu Poshana* and local tissue repair. By pacifying aggravated *Vata* and *Pitta* at the site, it reduces *Shula, Shotha*, and *Daha*, while promoting *Ropana*. Thus, *Murivenna* acts through transdermal *Sneha* absorption producing anti-inflammatory and regenerative effects.

INDIVIDUAL INGREDIENTS ACTING ON VRANA ROPANA

❖ *Karanja*^[11]

Due to its *Tikta* and *Katu Rasa*, *Karanja* helps in the *Shoshana* of *Kleda* and *Puya* present in *Dushta Vrana*, thereby facilitating wound cleansing and healing.

- *Karanjin* (Furanoflavonoid) – Anti oxidant, Antimicrobial; Reduces microbial colonization and oxidative stress, Promoting faster wound contraction
- *Pongamol*(flavonoid) – Anti-inflammatory; enhances fibroblast proliferation & collagen deposition.

❖ *Kumari*^[9]

Kumari exhibits *Raktagata Kleda Nashana* by reducing excessive moisture and fluid accumulation (*Jala Sanchaya*). In conditions of *Abhigata*, it promotes proper *Paka* of *Shopha*, thereby preventing complications and supporting healing.

- β -Sitosterol (Phytosterol) - Promotes angiogenesis and enhances re-epithelialization
- *Aloin* (Barbaloin) + Anthraquinone glycoside - Anti-inflammatory; reduces inflammatory mediators and supports epithelial regeneration.

❖ *Nagavalli*^[7]

Owing to its *Ushna Veerya*, *Nagavalli* effectively causes *Kleda* and *Kapha Shoshana*, thus maintaining dryness at the wound site and aiding the healing process.

- *Eugenol* (Phenolic compound) – Antimicrobial, Anti-inflammatory; accelerated epithelialization & wound contraction.
- *Hydroxychavicol* (Phenolic compound) – Antioxidant, prevents tissue damage & supports Granulation.

❖ *Palandu*^[17]

Palandu possesses *Shoola Hara* properties. According to *Gada Nigraha*, it also exhibits *Charma Shuddhi* action, contributing to purification and health of the skin.

- *Allicin* (organosulfur compound) – Broad spectrum Antimicrobial; Prevents wound infection & accelerates healing.

❖ *Shatavari*^[21]

Shatavari is characterized by *Madhura Rasa* and *Snigdha* and *Guru Guna*. Through its *Mamsa Poshana* property, it helps in restoring muscle tissue lost due to *Vrana*, thereby promoting tissue regeneration and wound healing.

- *Shatavarin I–IV* (Steroidal saponins) = Promote tissue regeneration, anti-inflammatory action, improve immune response at wound site
- *Quercetin* (flavonoid) = Enhances angiogenesis, reduces inflammation and oxidative stress in wounds
- *Asparagamine A*(alkaloid) = Antioxidant and cytoprotective effect aiding tissue repair

❖ *Shigru*^[13]

Due to its *Teekshna* and *Ushna Guna*, *Shigru* induces sweating and exhibits strong cleansing action. Its hot infusion is traditionally used in skin diseases. In cases of maggot-infested wounds, fresh bark paste applied over the wound and bandaged causes the maggots to come out due to its pungent odour.

- *Quercetin* + *Kaempferol* (Flavonoid) - Enhances Fibroblast migration & decreases inflammatory mediators

❖ *Paribhadra*^[15]

- *Erythraline* (Alkaloid) – exhibits Anti-Inflammatory & cytoprotective activity aiding tissue regeneration.

❖ *Vasuka*^[19]

- *Orientin* (Flavonoid) - Anti-Oxidant, Antimicrobial; Supports wound Contraction and Epithelial repair.
- *Ursolic acid* (Triterpenoid) -Stimulates collagen synthesis and Keratinocyte proliferation

❖ *Shali*^[23]

- *Ferulic acid* (Phenolic Acid) – Neutralizes free radicals; protects wound tissue from Oxidative stress
- *Gamma* – *oryzanol* (Ferulate ester of sterol) -Anti-inflammatory; enhances epithelial regeneration

❖ *Importance of Narikela Taila as Sneha Dravya*^[25]

Narikela Taila, with its *Sheeta Veerya* and *Snigdha Guna*, balances the *Ushna* and *Teekshna* attributes of other drugs, preventing excessive irritation. It acts as an ideal medium for topical application, facilitating sustained contact with tissues and aiding absorption. Its *Pittahara* and *Dahashamana* properties make *Murivenna* suitable even in burns and inflamed wounds.

CONCLUSION

Murivenna is a classical Ayurvedic formulation with specific utility in the management of *Vrana* and *Abhigatajanya* disorders. Its composition, dominated by *Tikta* and *Katu Rasa* with *Ushna Veerya*, addresses *Shotha*, *Vedana*, *Kleda of Dushta Vrana*. These components also commonly encounter *Abhigatajanya* conditions. *Shothahara*, *Vedanasthapana*, *Vishaghna*, *Krimighna*, and *Ropana* properties are due to the synergistic action of the ingredients. This supports to resolve the inflammation which facilitates the healthy tissue repair.

Murivenna is indicated in Acute & chronic condition of *Abhigatajanya Vrana* to differentiate the therapeutic action of these 2 conditions. In acute condition of *Vrana* and *Bhagna*, it should be applied in cold form as *Rakta* and *Vata* is involved. In chronic condition – to enhance the healing it can be applied in hot form.

Thus, *Murivenna* exemplifies the strength of regional *Anubhuta Yoga* traditions and reinforces their relevance in contemporary Ayurvedic practice. Further experimental and clinical studies are necessary to validate its traditional claims and support its integration into evidence-based wound care protocols.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author is grateful to the Department of *Rasashastra* and *Bhaishajya Kalpana* for the constant support and guidance.

REFERENCES

1. Acharya YT, editor. Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta, with Nibandhaangraha commentary by Dalhana. Chikitsasthana. Dvivraneeyachikitsitam adhyaya: Chapter 1, Verse 8. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukamba Sanskrit Sansthan, 2009; p. 7.
2. Anonymous. The Ayurvedic Formulary of India by Department of Ayush, Part 3, 7th Class, Formulation-23. 1st edition. New Delhi: The Controller of Publications, 2011; p.203.
3. Kunju Krishna Nadar MLA, editor (1st edition), Marma Shastra Peedika, 1975; p.219-220.
4. Kunju Krishna Nadar MLA, editor (1st edition), Marma Shastra Peedika, 1975; p.1155-1159.
5. Parameshwaran A, Varier K V R, Editor (1st edition); Yoga Manjari; Part 1, Thrissur; Neolith Printers, 2015; Pg 182 -183.
6. Murthy S K R. Bhavaprakasha of Bhavamishra. Volume 1. 1st Edition; Guduchyadi Varga, Chapter 6, Varanasi: Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy, 2004; p. 229.
7. Government of India. The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India. First Edition. Part 1, Volume 3. New Delhi: The Controller of Publications Civil Lines, 2008; p.131.
8. Mishra B, Vaishya R. 'Vidyotini' Hindi commentary on Bhavaprakasha by Bhavamishra. Purvakhand, Nigantu bhaga, Guduchyadi varga, verse 229. Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, 2007; p.419.
9. Government of India. Dravya Kosha volume 1, A compendium of medicinal plants of Tumkur and Shimoga Districts. Karnataka: Abhimaani Publications, 2012; p.261 -264.
10. Murthy S K R. Bhavaprakasha of Bhavamishra. Volume 1. 1st Edition; Guduchyadi Varga, Chapter 6, Varanasi: Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy, 2004; p. 246.
11. Government of India. Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India. Vol. 2, part 1. New Delhi: The controller of publications civil lines, 1999; p.79.
12. Murthy S K R. Bhavaprakasha of Bhavamishra. Volume 1. 1st Edition; Guduchyadi Varga, Chapter 6, verse 105. Varanasi: Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy, 2004; p. 244.
13. Government of India. Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India. Vol. 2, part 1. New Delhi: The controller of publications civil lines, 1999; p. 155.
14. Murthy S K R. Bhavaprakasha of Bhavamishra. Volume 1. 1st Edition; Guduchyadi Varga, Chapter 6, verse 100. Varanasi: Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy, 2004; p. 243.
15. Government of India. Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India. Vol. 2, part 1. New Delhi: The controller of publications civil lines, 1999; p. 135.
16. Mishra B, Vaishya R. 'Vidyotini' Hindi commentary on Bhavaprakasha by Bhavamishra. Purvakhand, Nigantu bhaga, Hareetakyadi varga, verse 226-227. Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, 2007; p.130.
17. Orient Warrier P K, Nambiar V P K, Ramankutty C, editor, (reprint edition); Indian Medicinal Plants, A compendium of 500 species; Volume 6; Chennai; Orient Longman Limited, 1997; p.254-256.
18. Mishra B, Vaishya R. 'Vidyotini' Hindi commentary on Bhavaprakasha of Bhavamishra. Pushpa Varga, verse 34. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, 2007; p. 481.
19. Orient Warrier P K, Nambiar V P K, Ramankutty C, editor, (reprint edition); Indian Medicinal Plants, A compendium of 500 species; Volume 5; Chennai; Orient Longman Limited, 1997; p.177-179.
20. Mishra B, Vaishya R. 'Vidyotini' Hindi commentary on Bhavaprakasha of Bhavamishra. Guduchyadi Varga, verse 184-185. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, 2007; p. 392.
21. Government of India. Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India. Vol. 4, part 1. New Delhi: The controller of publications civil lines, 2004; p. 108.
22. Mishra B, Vaishya R. 'Vidyotini' Hindi commentary on Bhavaprakasha of Bhavamishra. Dhanya Varga, verse 7. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, 2007; p. 635.
23. Government of India. Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India. Vol. 2, part 1. New Delhi: The controller of publications civil lines, 1999; p. 145.
24. Murthy S K R. Bhavaprakasha of Bhavamishra. Volume 1. 1st Edition; Amradi phala Varga, Chapter 6, Varanasi: Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy, 2004; p. 313.
25. Government of India. Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India. Part 1, Vol. 5. Delhi: The controller of publications civil lines, 2008; p. 134-45.